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The extension of the perspective of the physical quantities of length, mass and time by introducing the external and internal coordinate system, as well as the complex coordinate axis, and thereby a novel approach to the dual nature of matter

Einstein developed a revolutionary new theory and his theory of relativity opened a new perspective in the world of physics. $E=m*c^2$, developed for the relationship between mass and energy, directed attention to a new field of research: in addition to the research of force fields, to the practical use of atomic energy. The results achieved and explored in this latter field confirmed the experimental implementation of the theory.

These new achievements make it necessary to analyse the new experimental results – including the $E=m*c^2$ law – through the law of conservation of energy and to consider consistency with it as an important principle.

There is a need to analyse how we can interpret and justify this law by extending it to quantum mechanics. In the debate between Einstein and Bohr, Bohr argued that the particle and wave nature of the mass of an atomic particle, even a photon, cannot be demonstrated simultaneously, which can only be determined based on the decision of our measurement. In this regard, we cannot ignore the provisions of Heisenberg's uncertainty relation, according to which the measurement of the position and momentum of a particle cannot be measured simultaneously with arbitrary accuracy, the combined error value of their measurement shows a value above an error limit. Based on these, we must strive to support the finding of a consistent mathematical structure in which either Einstein's or Bohr's position naturally appears.

To provide a mathematical structure that ensures this, we must move from the set of real numbers to the set of complex numbers, and we must distinguish between external and internal coordinate values - which I have applied and deemed necessary.

Most physical quantities can be given by the fundamental physical quantities of length – mass – time (in CGS, MKS or SI system). Without going into the field of philosophy and history of science, we must accept that these basic quantities exist independently of the existence of humanity, because they already existed when they were not measured, or even dealt with. Time passed independently of people, bodies had weight, mass, and speed even if they only experienced that the leopard runs faster than them, while they leave a greater distance behind them than snails in a certain time.

Then, with the development of science, scientists defined these, determined their units of measurement, then recorded the measured data, and even marked them on a number line, on a coordinate axis. These were determined by external measurements, I called these measured, visible and detectable data external coordinate values.

In the world of classical mechanics, this measurement was sufficient to describe the phenomena of the world, but the development of technology and science has stretched this framework.

The interest in areas beyond the finite dimensions of our Earth, from space exploration to the study of distant galaxies, has broadened the need to understand our universe. This research includes the work of Lorenz, which, in addition to the finite, real value of the speed of light, was aimed at its virtuality, as well as Einstein's theory of relativity, and the latest stage of the scientific revolution that unfolded with him, which seeks the answer to the secrets of the depths of quantum mechanics.

During his research on the speed of light, Lorenz created a transformation formula when examining the speed, and called the resulting speed value virtual. He also determined the virtual distance based on the virtual speed. However, these values are state parameters that are not visible to us, external observers, and are not directly accessible. Therefore, these values can be defined as the internal coordinate values of speed and distance/path, in distinction from the external coordinate values that we measure and can measure (named above). These quantities – which we do not perceive, but must nevertheless be considered existing, and which we can no longer express numerically in our existing real coordinate system – can only be concretized on the set of complex numbers, on our complex coordinate system, i.e. expressed in the form of complex numbers.

These thoughts lead us to interpret Lorenz's analytical research based on the above principles, to extend the transformation formula he applied to the physical concepts of length – mass – time, to create it, and to determine the consequences from its results.

External and internal coordinate value of speed

Lorenz, before Einstein, created the transformation named after him for the speed of light, and called its infinite pattern virtual:

$$\mathbf{L\ transform} = \mathbf{1 / (1 - v^2 / c^2)^{1/2}}$$

This transformation introduced by Lorenz does not take place in real space, but by involving the complex coordinate axis. This mathematical “bridge” explains why we see as finite what is (virtually) infinite according to Lorenz’s designation.

The transformation relation introduced by Lorenz for the velocity v, denoted as Lv, can be written in the following form:

$$Lv(v) = v * (1 / (1 - v^2 / c^2)^{1/2})$$

and the writing in complex form can be done based on the following:

The internal coordinate value Lv(v) obtained by the Lv-transformation shows the magnitude and absolute value of the given physical quantity.

The external and internal coordinates and thus their values can be connected using complex numbers. By defining these two coordinate forms, we can build a new method of analysis and investigation by displaying them on the complex number set.

The general form of complex numbers is:

$$X': (x, y) = (x + y * i)$$

where

x is the real part of the quantity,

y is the imaginary part,

i is the imaginary unit.

In order to write down the individual Lv(v) values, the above plane must be defined as a complex number.

imaginary part

The external coordinate of the physical quantity is x , a real number, the internal coordinate is given by the Lorentz transformation $\langle L(x) \rangle$, which – using the Pythagorean theorem – is a complex number in the following form.

The internal coordinate of the quantity X is given by the complex number

$$X: (x, (\langle L(x) \rangle^2 - x^2)^{1/2})$$

i.e.

$$X = x + (\langle L(x) \rangle^2 - x^2)^{1/2} * i = x + (L(x)^2 - x^2)^{1/2} * i.$$

Applied to velocity

The internal coordinate of the velocity is given by:

$$L_v(v) = v + (\langle L_v(v) \rangle^2 - v^2)^{1/2} * i = v + (L_v(v))^2 - v^2)^{1/2} * i.$$

External and internal coordinate value of distance

To determine the internal coordinate value of distance, we can use Lorentz's derivation, which he derived from the velocity.

If two inertial frames move along the x axis with a relative velocity v , according to the Lorentz-derived transformation of distance X

$$x' = (x - v * t) / (1 - v^2 / c^2)^{1/2}$$

$$\text{i.e. } L_v(x) = (x - v * t) / (1 - v^2 / c^2)^{1/2}.$$

External and internal coordinate value of time

People have always observed the change of time, and then calculated it in relation to something. These reference points were initially linked to some physical phenomenon, e.g. the full moon or the beginning of a ruler's work, but they slowly led to an accepted time calculation. The units of time were linked to the day (rotation around the earth's axis) and the year (rotation around the sun). This made it possible to indicate which year before or after our time calculation the event occurred. Finally, after the development of science, it was now linked to the existence of the universe, the period from the creation of our universe to the final explosion that will occur - that is, from the big bang to the

apocalypse. This scientific approach places events in a closed time interval - inseparable from our material world - based on our external measurement. This gives us the external coordinate system of time.

However, "time", as a physical concept and quantity in a broader sense, existed before the big bang and will exist after the apocalypse. This time, the existence of time as its essence, constitutes the value of the internal coordinate of time. (Mathematically stated: an interval open in both directions.)

After this introduction, it can be stated that the Lorenz transformation can also be created for time. (Lt).

For this, we need to find a suitable time calculation point as a special element and determine its precise definition, and we also need to distinguish between events before and after our time calculation.

According to this, the description of time in the internal coordinate system consists of two parts, the semi-closed intervals of negative (past) and positive (future) time, which the PRESENT POINT separates into two parts. (Mathematically denoted (] and [)) The following figure provides guidance for this:

Present Point

big bang apocalypse

t (big bang, Present) t (Present, apocalypse)

According to the diagram, time, viewed from the Present Point, consists of two infinite sections, from $-\infty$ to the P-point and from the P-point to $+\infty$.

Its peculiarity is that the PRESENT POINT is not stationary, but moves in the direction of the positive semi-axis at every moment. At the PRESENT POINT in the internal coordinate system, time is constant, i.e. when we stand at that point, we always **perceive the 'present moment'(!)**, because we can only move on the real value. We cannot enter the domain of complex time, while time passes on the real, external coordinate axis, and we grow old.

Consequently, the Lt-transformation for time must be given differently for the two domains. In the past, for negative t values

$$Lt(t) = t / (1 - t^2 / t_{\text{big bang}}^2)^{1/2}$$

and in the future, when t values are positive

$$Lt(t) = t / (1 - t^2 / t_{\text{apocalypse}}^2)^{1/2}.$$

The internal coordinate value of time in complex form

$$K(t) = t + (Lt(t)^2 - t^2)^{1/2} * i$$

where

$$Lt(t) = t / (1 - t^2 / t_{\text{lim}}^2)^{1/2},$$

the t_{lim} is $t_{\text{big bang}}$ OR $t_{\text{apocalypse}}$

The peculiarity of $K(t)$ is that it has only one real value, AT THE PRESENT POINT, which is constantly moving through time. This moment is the point where external and internal values are the same and both are real. As a result, we can only influence phenomena and intervene in events in the present moment, the event cannot be modified retroactively, and the event cannot be determined for the future, it has multiple outcomes.

External and internal coordinate value of mass

In the times before the 20th century, classical mechanics proved to be sufficient for the investigation of mass and the phenomena related to it. However, for the discoveries made at the end of the 19th century and in the 20th century and for their explanation, new ways had to be sought, which became necessary primarily as a result of the researches developing in the fields of electronics, then relativity theory, and quantum mechanics.

The matter and wave nature of mass became an important and researchable question as a result of the debate between Einstein and Bohr. The two forms of appearance have always excited physicists and they have been trying to give a theoretical answer or find experimental evidence that would decide this question: Does the matter and wave appearance/existence form always exist regardless of our observation, or does mass only take on the matter or wave appearance form depending on our decision?

When determining the matter and wave nature of mass, one must start from the difficult problem that the dual nature of the smallest unit mass, the atomic particle, is known and experimentally proven to physicists, but the fundamental reason and explanation for this has not yet been sufficiently well-founded.

In practice, we know the parts of atoms, their structure, the mass of protons, neutrons and electrons (and their even smaller particles), but at the same time we are aware of their wave nature. Research and theories are constantly discovering smaller atomic parts, they always arrive at newer and newer ones, but not at the smallest particle. If we assume a series of further research, during which we arrive at smaller and smaller components, we must say that we cannot reach the smallest atomic particle in a finite step. The smallest part will be the particle with zero mass, possessing “merely” wave nature, but we can never reach this particle by dividing the non-zero mass part a finite number of times. All these considerations led to extend the theoretical considerations of the internal and external coordinate system also to mass.

My assumption is that the smallest elementary particle that we measure is located in our external coordinate system. A zero-mass particle, which contains only wave character and which can never be obtained by a finite number of divisions of a non-zero mass particle, is the form of appearance of the smallest non-zero mass particle in terms of the internal coordinate. A transformation must be found such that the value of $L(m)$ obtained by this L transformation – appearing in the internal coordinate – tends towards zero and its limit value is $L(m_0) = 0$.

A modified form of the Lorenz transformation leads to achieving these goals. The first step was to find a suitable form of the applicable L transformation.

$$L(m) = m * (1 - m_0^2 / m^2)^{1/2}$$

where m (in decreasing value) approaches m_0 along the external coordinate.

In the following, we write the value of m in the form $n.m_0$, which means the n -fold multiple of the smallest particle. m is a discrete multiple of the smallest m_0 value $n.m_0$, which converges to m_0 in the limit $n \rightarrow 1$)

Using this form $m = n.m_0$, where $n > = 1$

$$L(n.m_0) = n m_0 \sqrt{1 - m_0^2 / (n.m_0)^2}$$

we get the form, from which

$$L(m) = L(n.m_0) = n m_0 \sqrt{1 - 1/n^2} = n m_0 \frac{\sqrt{n^2 - 1}}{n}$$

$$L(m) = m_0 \sqrt{n^2 - 1}$$

If $n = 1$, then

$$L(m_0) = 0,$$

i.e. for the smallest non-zero mass elementary particle, the internal coordinate system shows zero mass! **For every smallest elementary particle, and any type of it, when**

$n = 1$, then: $L(m) = 0$.

According to this, the particle crosses this threshold in complex space massless and as a wave. This model therefore treats the wave – particle duality not as a mystery, but as the result of a geometric transformation between coordinate systems.

In the case of the physical quantities i discussed so far, the relation $L(i) > i$ existed, but now, in the case of the transformation applied to the mass, the relation

$$L(m) < m$$

exists, therefore the method of defining the imaginary introduced earlier must be modified.

In the case of the previously applied method, the external coordinate axis was made to correspond to the real axis of the complex number, and this method must be followed in our present case as well.

The figure below shows the indicated difference, according to which the inverse method according to the lower sketch of the figure must be applied to the mass:

imaginary part

imaginary part

If we take the value of the internal axis as the real part and construct the imaginary part using the perpendicular axis set to the vector $L(x)$,

internal

it can be seen that the internal axis, based on which we would determine the imaginary part, would not be a straight axis, and for all values calculated on the internal axis, the imaginary part would be m_0 .

$$\text{imaginary part}^2 = (n m_0)^2 - (L(n \cdot m_0))^2 = (n m_0)^2 - (n^2 - 1) m_0^2 = m_0^2,$$

i.e., for this formation form, for all n , the

$$\text{imaginary part} = m_0.$$

However, the form of the imaginary number must be determined from the external coordinate (we also corresponded to the real axis in the previous derivations).

Thus, the $L(n m_0)$ vector must be related to the external coordinate axis, and therefore, in the right-angled triangle belonging to the inverse shape, the real part is not given by the external axis

$$m = n * m_0 \text{ point,}$$

but by the base point of the triangle's altitude line, and the imaginary part (y) can be determined by the altitude line of the triangle.

The real part of the complex form of the mass in terms of internal coordinates is the segment x_1 of the hypotenuse of the triangle up to the altitude point, and the imaginary part is the altitude belonging to the hypotenuse, which is equal to the geometric mean of its two segments x_1 and x_2 :

$$y = \sqrt{x_1 x_2}$$

By the similarity of the "large" and inner triangles

$$\frac{m_0 \sqrt{n^2 - 1}}{n \cdot m_0} = \frac{\sqrt{x_1 x_2}}{m_0}$$

$$m_0 \sqrt{n^2 - 1} = n \sqrt{x_1 x_2}$$

$$m_0^2 (n^2 - 1) = n^2 (x_1 x_2)$$

$$x_1 x_2 = m_0^2 \frac{(n^2 - 1)}{n^2}$$

from which

$$y = \sqrt{X_1 X_2} = m_0 \frac{\sqrt{n^2 - 1}}{n}$$

Based on the similarity of the two “small” triangles

$$\frac{x_1}{m_0 \sqrt{n^2 - 1}} = \frac{y}{m_0} = \frac{m_0 \sqrt{n^2 - 1}}{n}$$

from which

$$X_1 = \frac{m_0(n^2 - 1)}{n}$$

Similarly,

$$\frac{x_2}{m_0} = \frac{y}{m_0 \sqrt{n^2 - 1}} = \frac{m_0 \sqrt{n^2 - 1}}{m_0 \sqrt{n^2 - 1}}$$

from which

$$X_2 = \frac{m_0}{n}$$

The complex number form of the mass, including the external and internal coordinates

$$K(n m_0) = x_1 + y * i = x_1 + (x_1 * x_2)^{1/2} * i$$

$$K(n m_0) = m_0 / n * (n^2 - 1) + m_0 / n * (n^2 - 1)^{1/2} * i,$$

i.e.

$$K(n \cdot m_0) = \frac{m_0(n^2 - 1)}{n} + \frac{m_0}{n} \sqrt{n^2 - 1} * i$$

The value of the internal coordinate m_0 in complex form ($n=1$):

$$K(1 * m_0) = \frac{m_0(n^2 - 1)}{n} + \frac{m_0}{n} \sqrt{n^2 - 1} \cdot i = 0 + 0 * i \text{ real value.}$$

Regarding the representation of mass, we can make the following statements:

- 1./ The values of mass exist in the form $n \times m_0$, where n takes on values of (1, 2, 3 ...). m_0 is the smallest elementary mass particle, i.e. the smallest, “non-0” mass value. The values of mass are located on the external coordinate, which we perceive as an external observer.
- 2./ The elements of the internal coordinate $Lm(nm_0)$ are located on the internal coordinate axis.
- 3./ The value of $Lm(1m_0) = Lm(m_0)$ is 0, i.e. $= 0 + 0 \times i$ is a real value.
- 4./ The internal and external coordinate axes have a single common point, the 0 point.
- 5./ The point $Lm(m_0)$ is on both axes due to the common 0 point, the origin point.

The mass m_0 and $Lm(m_0)$ are both elements of the external coordinate, i.e. on the external coordinate the external observer perceives or can perceive both the mass of the elementary particle with mass m_0 – not 0 – and the value $Lm(m_0)$ ($=0$) according to the internal coordinate of the particle.

Consequently, while examining the smallest mass as a material particle, one can also perceive the particle with mass 0 $Lm(m_0)$. It can be seen that on the external coordinate the atomic, material particle can be perceived in both the matter and wave nature. The dual nature of matter can be grasped!

After this, let us turn to the great debate of quantum mechanics, which developed between Einstein and Bohr. One of the pivotal points of the debate between them was the dual nature of matter mentioned above, and we can (also) identify it with this question.

According to Einstein's hypothesis, the dual character of matter and wave – that is, according to my theory, $L(m_0)$ and m_0 – coexist ab ovo, are present at the same time. Bohr, on the other hand, assumed that the nature of an elementary particle is neither matter nor wave until we determine the method of observation, whether to identify it as mass or wave, that is, it can only be displayed during measurement, by forcing the measurement.

If we take the principle of conservation of energy as the most important basis for the decision, let us consider the particle with mass m_0 . According to Einstein's theory, this particle

carries energy $E = m_0 * c^2$

a wave particle of mass m_0

$$E = Lm(m_0) * c^2 = 0$$

Given that the speed of light c is finite /finite value, not infinite/, the combined energy of the two simultaneously present forms of appearance is: $E = m_0 * c^2$.

In order for a wave-nature particle to be able to transmit energy after any physical transformation, an "even smaller" elementary particle must be found, or should be found, that can provide this function.

Considering Bohr's theory, it depends on our decision whether the particle with matter or wave nature will be the result of the decision.

If the result of the decision is the m_0 material part, this naturally carries the energy of $E = m_0 * c^2$,

If the result of the decision is the wave-nature particle with mass 0, then this must have the same energy (!) as $E = m_0 * c^2$ and carry it further or transmit it further during further physical processes.

If we continue the theoretical consideration formulated above, then the energy $E = m_0 * c^2$ can be represented in the internal coordinate system, as a set of complex numbers

$$E = Lm(m_0) * (Lv(c))^2$$

carries energy, which it can theoretically transmit after any further physical transformation.

This theoretical model naturally leads to the interpretation of Bohr complementarity, without introducing new local hidden variables.

Let's take an example: put a pencil in a glass of water, slanted to the side of the glass, so that it is completely covered by the water. We can only grasp the upper end of the pencil if we put our hand in the glass and guide our hand in the same medium in which we perceive the pencil, i.e. we enter the medium of the pencil (the internal system).

Let's look at an analogous experiment:

Let's look at the above figure through a prism. Choose a prism that, using which, based on the refraction, the "image" of m_0 is placed on $Lm(m_0)$. Let's put a black ball in place of m_0 , and a transparent glass ball in place of $Lm(m_0)$. Let's fix this position of the prism.

We try to touch the image of the glass ball with our hand. This fails, we can only do it if we place our hand on the black ball while looking through the prism.

Based on these, let us imagine a pair of glasses with one lens empty (we can see through it freely), while in place of the other lens there is a prism set exactly according to the above.

Similarly, to touch the black ball, we have to look through the empty lens and guide our hand, and we can touch the glass ball by touching the black ball through the prism.

Returning to the basic situation, it can be stated that the corresponding conditions exist in the case of the external and internal coordinate systems.

If we want to see and examine the non-0-mass elementary particle m_0 , then the examination must be carried out on the empty glasses according to the external coordinates with an external perspective, and if the wave-like particle with 0 mass, then the examination must be carried out on the glass of the prism according to the internal coordinates. If we use only one eye at a time, then it is precisely decided which ball we see, whether we look with our naked eye or through the prism.

When we examine the particles on the coordinate axis, we can find the same elementary particle at two real(!) coordinate values! There are both places related to the dual nature of the elementary particle, where we can perceive it, but physically – simultaneously(!) – the particle cannot be duplicated. So, we can perceive the elementary particle at the scale values 0 and m_0 , depending on how we measure, examine, and decide. According to the example of prismatic glasses, in reality we perceive the elementary particle depending on whether we perform an examination according to the external or internal coordinate. Like all analogies, this one cannot give the completeness of the phenomenon, but it can give some sense of it.

We focus our investigation on how the two forms of appearance are connected and able to ensure this entanglement between each other, that is, that the two forms of appearance are preserved until the measurement is made.

Here I refer again to a simple example. Let's take a room with two mirrors on opposite sides. If we stand in front of the mirror and leave its field of view, our image does the same. The real figure and its image move together throughout the entire series of visible mirrors, that is, the image of the real figure is connected up to the reflection of the last mirror. Obviously, the image of us reaches the mirror, from there back, and further, the process of movement also takes place in this entanglement. However, through the speed of light! What is the speed between the two images? How is the entanglement created?

Let's return to what was described at the beginning of the study for the sake of a thought, where I referred to Einstein's mass-energy equivalence relation. Based on the study conducted, we can say that the energy is the same in both the external and internal coordinate systems, so

$$m_0 * c^2 = Lm(m_0) * (Lc(c))^2$$

equality must hold regardless of the coordinate systems used in the analysis based on the mass – energy constancy. We must refer to this as the basic principle of our analysis. Since our decision or measurement determines the appearance of the particle, both forms must in principle carry the mass-energy equivalence, and based on the conservation of energy, it must be ensured by the existence of equality depending on the decision. This is only possible in case of $Lm(m_0) = 0$ with infinite value of $Lc(c)$ in the internal coordinate system.

From this it follows that the feedback of the wave-nature particle can arrive back at infinite speed “without delay”. If we accept this reasoning, the “spooky” nature of the coupling seems to be resolved (also).

REFERENCE

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